

CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES IN THE BRAZILIAN EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT IN RELATION TO SPECIAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the theme of challenges and perspectives in the Brazilian educational context in relation to special education. This is an extremely necessary and highly complex subject, because it involves more than just theoretical knowledge, requiring long-term empirical studies of a multidisciplinary nature. Its main objective is to present the challenges and perspectives in the educational context. The work is the result of an exploratory bibliographic survey, covering historical milestones, from the Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988 as well

as current Public Policies. The studies carried out indicate that even though Public Policies conceive Special Education under the perspective of School Inclusion and the right of all to Education, many limitations still persist for People with special needs regarding access to Education in regular schools, as well as in the implementation of quality Education, since, historically, the right to Education of People with special needs in Brazil has been neglected. The considerations made in this study indicate that the main challenges in special education consist of the lack of training for teachers, considering that they need to develop diversified and adapted activities in view of the specificity of the students.

Keywords: Special education. Including education. Salamanca Declaration. Effective public policies. People with special needs.

INTRODUCTION

Special education is a construct that comes in the wake of studies that prove the ability of individuals with some kind of disability to effectively participate in social life, as long as the conditions of access and activities relevant to each individual's interests are adapted. This demonstrates a great advance in thinking about inclusion, because it allows the creation of conditions for dialogue, studies, research and investments, both in social and pedagogical practices, including improvements in physical structures and teaching procedures aimed at this specific group.

Much has been achieved in terms of offering education characterized by adapted and other developed methodologies, with the aim of enabling them to learn easily and to their potential. However, many empirical studies need to be carried out in order to implement the proposal, because in addition to inclusion, this group must be guaranteed the right to comprehensive learning.

This study seeks to present the challenges and perspectives of special education considering the need to rethink the educational processes aimed at this specific audience, as well as the strategies used in the classroom. In this sense, the following question was taken as a starting point for the development of this study: What are the main challenges and perspectives that present themselves to inclusive education?

In response to this question, the main objective of this research is to present the challenges and perspectives in the educational context, referring to this pedagogical mechanism that aims to include individuals who have some kind of disability in the regular formal education space, emphasizing that the objective goes beyond simply including them; it is expected that they learn and master the systematic curricular contents. In this sense, the specific objectives are: a) to seek information in studies carried out on the challenges in special

education; b) to identify what the perspectives are for the inclusion of special education in regular schools; c) to understand the main factors related to special education in the educational context.

The hypothesis adopted here is that the challenges in the educational context consist, above all, in the lack of teacher training considering the need to apply inclusion in the classroom, given that many teachers have difficulty adapting curricular pedagogical activities for students with special needs, which means that inclusion is nothing more than a bureaucratic process, when it should be a didactic process, capable of fostering the cognitive and intellectual transformation of special students, respecting their learning limits and global capabilities.

This study is justified by the need to address this issue, considering that, despite the guidelines in official documents regarding the process of inclusion of students with special needs, there are still obstacles that impact the effective inclusion of these students in regular education spaces. The relevance of this study is to promote a reflection on the importance of special education considering the challenges and perspectives in the educational context. The target audience for this study is professionals who work in education and others interested in understanding some aspects related to special education.

WHAT OFFICIAL DOCUMENTS SAY ABOUT SPECIAL EDUCATION

Special Education is advocated and guaranteed, in an integral manner, respecting all pedagogical and didactic parameters, by the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (Law 9394/96), in its chapter V, article 58, as *verbatim*: “[...] the modality of school education, offered preferably in the regular education system, for students with special needs” (Brazil, 1996, sp). It is worth highlighting that the concept of Special Education, presented in article 3 of Resolution CNE/CEB 02/2001, defines it as a

[...] modality of school education, it is understood as an educational process defined by a pedagogical proposal that ensures special educational resources and services, institutionally organized to support, complement, supplement and, in some cases, replace common educational services, in order to guarantee school education and promote the development of the potential of students who present special educational needs, in all stages and modalities of basic education (Brazil, 2001, sp).

In view of the above, it is important to understand that, in July 1994, the World Conference on Special Education took place in Spain, in the city of Salamanca, in which, through declarations, an agreement was reached between the delegates representing 88

governments and 25 international organizations, and thus, they prepared a guiding document aimed at the target audience of special education and which was categorized as the Salamanca Declaration, which highlights that, “the educational planning prepared by governments should focus on education for all people in all regions of the country and in all economic conditions, through public and private schools” (Salamanca Declaration, 1994, sp).

In 2001, CNE/CEB Resolution 02/2001 was enacted, which determines in its article 2 that:

Education systems must enroll all students, and schools must organize themselves to serve students with special educational needs, ensuring the necessary conditions for a quality education for all. Sole paragraph. Education systems must be aware of the real demand for serving students with special educational needs, by creating information systems and establishing an interface with government agencies responsible for the School Census and the Demographic Census, in order to meet all the variables implicit in the quality of the educational process of these students (Brazil, 2001, sp).

What can be seen in this resolution is that there is an imperative [*or at least it attempts to do so*] regarding the inclusion of all students who present some specific disability in regular school units; however, it does not present any type of formative didactic-pedagogical guidance on how to work with such individuals, since they are inserted among groups of others who have educational demands that are different from their own. It is not about solving the problem of exclusion/inclusion; the issue of learning is a primary factor when talking about education and its principles and dynamic processes.

The *Salamanca Declaration* presents some important points that serve as guidance for a reflective pedagogical process, considering the changes in contemporary times. Therefore, it points out that:

- Every child has a fundamental right to education and must be given the opportunity to achieve and maintain an adequate level of learning;
- Every child has unique characteristics, interests, abilities and learning needs;
- Educational systems should be designed and educational programs implemented to take into account the wide diversity of such characteristics and needs;
- Those with special educational needs must have access to regular school, which should accommodate them within a child-centered pedagogy capable of satisfying such needs;
- Regular schools, which have such an inclusive orientation, constitute the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society and achieving education for all; moreover, such schools provide an effective education to the majority of children and improve the efficiency and, ultimately, the cost-effectiveness of

the entire educational system (Salamanca Declaration, 1994, n.d.).

Thus, school inclusion, even strengthened by the Salamanca Declaration (1994), does not solve all the problems related to inclusion processes, given the marginalization that occurs with people with special needs, because the exclusion process occurs at birth or, precisely, at the moment some type of physical disability appears. In addition to marginalization, in 2004 Law 3,298 underwent changes due to the enactment of the *Accessibility Law*, according to Decree No. 5,296 of 2004. The aforementioned Law establishes a *classification panorama* for those with disabilities ⁸:

Decree, the following shall be considered:

I - Person with a disability [...] is a person who has a limitation or incapacity to perform an activity and falls into the following categories:

- a) physical disability: complete or partial alteration of one or more segments of the human body, leading to impairment of physical function, presenting itself in the form of paraplegia, paraparesis, monoplegia, monoparesis, tetraplegia, tetraparesis, triplegia, triparesis, hemiplegia, hemiparesis, ostomy, amputation or absence of a limb, cerebral palsy, dwarfism, limbs with congenital or acquired deformity, except for aesthetic deformities and those that do not produce difficulties in the performance of functions;
- b) hearing impairment: bilateral, partial or total loss, of forty-one decibels (dB) or more, measured by audiogram at frequencies of 500Hz, 1,000Hz, 2,000Hz and 3,000Hz.
- c) visual impairment: blindness, in which visual acuity is equal to or less than 0.05 in the best eye, with the best optical correction; low vision, which means visual acuity between 0.3 and 0.05 in the best eye, with the best (Brazil, 2004, sp).

In 2013, Law No. 9,394 of 1996 underwent changes and, within the scope of Education for People with Disabilities, this change occurs notably in its Article 4, section III, amended by Law No. 12,796 of 2013. Based on this change, it was established that “free specialized educational services for students with disabilities, global developmental disorders and high abilities or giftedness, transversal to all levels, stages and modalities, should be, preferably, in the regular education system” (Brazil, 2013, sp).

In 2015, Law No. 13,146 was enacted, known as the *Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities* (Statute of Persons with Disabilities), which aims to ensure and promote, under equal conditions, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by persons with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and citizenship (Brazil, 2015). In view of this, it is clear that official documents indicate that the rights of people with special needs are

⁸However, this terminology is then replaced (later) by Person with Disability, the change is made with the aim of breaking cultural stereotypes about these individuals (Authors' note, 2025).

enforced. However, despite the existence of these documents, there are many challenges related to the inclusion of these students, especially with regard to issues related to teaching and learning conditions.

EXCLUSION : IMPACTS ON STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

Regarding social exclusion, which is still an evident problem in society, it is necessary to rethink practices and strategies in the teaching and learning process, given the inclusion of students in schools, considering that deficient learning condemns, once again, the individual to social stigmatization and consequent exclusion from the means of production. According to Hunter (2004, p. 2-3), “social exclusion can be defined as multiple deprivations resulting from a lack of personal, social, political or financial opportunities. The notion of social exclusion refers to inadequate social participation and a lack of social integration.”

It is worth noting that, when speaking of the excluded, reference is made to the denial of established rights; therefore, it is interesting to note that the Federal Constitution of 1988, through its Art. 5, (Brazil, 2010, p. 17) states that “all are equal before the law, without distinction of any nature, guaranteeing Brazilians and foreigners residing in the country the inviolability of the right to life, liberty, equality, security and property”.

According to Sasaki (1997, p. 38), “social integration consisted of the effort to insert into society people who had disabilities and reached a certain level of capacity compatible with existing social standards”. Regarding the importance and need to promote continuing education, Albres and Neves (2014) highlight that,

Training, then, more than teaching them techniques and methodologies, should provide them with this reflective space and the power to analyze their own classes, to create based on their own experiences and to be open to change. We noted the tensions at the beginning of their careers due to the lack of training and the feelings of anguish, so they were building their ways of conducting classes intuitively, and when they came across a new training course with 'scientific knowledge' and 'didactic knowledge' they began to redefine their practices (Albres and Neves, 2014, p. 86). [The emphasis is in the original]

What needs to be clarified is that when the teacher does not have control over the situation, his/her defense mechanism is to abandon the situation; therefore, adequate training involves in-depth knowledge of the psychology of the object in which its behavior is clarified in order to allow decision-making in teaching and learning situations. Methodologies, pedagogical and didactic strategies arise from empirical knowledge of the objects and their

attitudes. Theoretical training, disconnected from empirical actions of observation and action, contributes very little to overcoming the problem, because, as very little or almost nothing is known about the cognitive processes of this target audience, the supposed classes of studies remain in the affective aspect and from there they cannot advance, creating wonderful discourses, but which prove inept in the face of reality.

THE INCLUSION OF STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN THE SCHOOL CONTEXT

Regarding inclusion, teachers need to become aware of the need to adapt school activities considering the specificities of each student, including those with special needs. To do so, they need to adopt pedagogical strategies for assessment. Therefore, training processes aimed at self-knowledge and the search for transformation are necessary, in order to develop effective conducts for teaching and learning processes, considering the wide diversity of students' needs (Omote & Vieira, 2018).

Mantoan (1999) clarifies that, “inclusion implies a change in educational perspective, as it does not only affect students with disabilities and those who have learning difficulties, but everyone else so that they can achieve success in the general educational stream” (Mantoan, 1999, 2015, p. 28).

As Ferreira (2005) points out, Inclusive Education must have as its perspective a reflective action that considers the diversity and personalities of each subject, aiming at learning (qualitative and significant) and, with that, personal and social appreciation. With that, it is appropriate to present the concept of inclusion, which according to Sasaki (1997, p. 41) refers to the “process by which society adapts to be able to include people with special needs in its general social systems and, simultaneously, these people prepare to assume their roles in society”. However, this change in thinking and empirical stance demands empirical knowledge on the subject. The way it has been treated, what it does is merely the forced acceptance of such individuals in social environments without them having the proper opportunity to demonstrate their dynamic value.

According to Ferreira and Guimarães (2003, p. 44),

It is necessary to rethink the meaning of pedagogical practice in order to try to avoid the mistakes of the past, when students with disabilities were left on the sidelines. These individuals must be guaranteed support and encouragement so that they can participate and collaborate in the planning and well-being of this new type of society, because the social value of equality is

consistent and pertinent with the practice of quality education for all (Ferreira and Guimarães, 2003, p. 44).

Regarding pedagogical practice, teachers are challenged daily in the classroom by students; therefore, it becomes necessary for educators to see the specificity of each of them, recognizing their particularities and unique learning abilities. Therefore, for schools to make their pedagogical and didactic practices truly inclusive, that is, receptive to diversity, it is essential to transform their thinking regarding strategies, lesson planning, assessment of the teaching-learning process, training and development of teachers, especially those who work in elementary education. In addition to innovations, it is worth highlighting that “inclusion implies a different fusion, which unites regular education with special education in order to offer diverse and expanded alternatives to improve the quality of education for all students” (Belisário, 2005, p. 130).

In view of this, it is understood that the challenges faced by teachers in relation to the teaching and learning process of students with special needs are many and characteristic, considering that, in many specific cases, teachers do not have the appropriate training to understand the specificities of each student and, therefore, what we have is the ineptitude of the system in the face of the problem, in which it seeks to respond to society through accusations against the systems, *denouncing* neglect towards such students.

The solution involves knowledge about the psychology of the object and, from there, seeking innovative solutions in the fields of teaching and learning, and this is only possible through empirical research, that is, the classroom must be the laboratory that will promote such answers to questions that have not yet been clarified; therefore, not understood.

CONCLUSION

This study sought to understand the importance of understanding the challenges and perspectives in the educational context, with regard to special education and its paradigms, highlighting the issue of inclusion and exclusion of individuals with special needs. It was found that official documents advocate the broad and unrestricted right to inclusion in the teaching-learning process, considering the guarantee that access to education for such individuals is not denied.

In this context, some laws, decrees and other documents were presented that point to the right to education for people with special needs, in which such documents aim to guide and direct the teaching and learning process, aiming to enable society to coexist broadly, respecting

its limits, as well as seeking to minimize discrimination, with a view to the realization of human rights, with the inclusion of people with special needs in the job market being of utmost importance, so that they can play their role in the broad and unrestricted exercise of citizenship.

The considerations made in this study indicate that the main challenges in special education consist of the lack of teacher training, considering that they need to develop diversified activities for students as well as adapted ones, given the specificity of the students. In addition to training, it is necessary to reflect on strategies that provide the inclusion of students with special needs.

This study broadly clarifies that teacher training goes beyond offering them theoretical support and knowledge about this or that specific disability; because the teacher's actions will be about and in relation to the child, and each of them will present a *unique behavior*, requiring interventions of equal nature and proportion. Thus, we are not talking about knowledge; but about knowing how to do and even what not to do in certain situations.

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